

Action of Hydrogen Sulphide on Insoluble Chromates, Part I. Lead Chromate and Silver Chromate.

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Dunnicliff and Soni (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, **33**, 81) showed that hydrogen sulphide decomposes potassium chromate with the formation of chromium hydroxide, sulphur, potassium thiosulphate and potassium polysulphide. Dunnicliff and Kotwani (*ibid.*, 1931, **35**, 3214) showed that, on similar reduction, chromic acid gives chromium sulphate, chromium thiosulphate, chromium hydroxide and sulphur.

When hydrogen sulphide is passed through a suspension of freshly precipitated lead chromate in water, the orange colour first changes to dull brown and then through various shades until, after about 24 hours, a greenish black solid residue is formed. The neutral filtrate and washing contained no sulphur acid except hydrogen sulphide.

The precipitate contained lead sulphide, chromium sulphate, and thiosulphate (partly co-ordinated), chromium hydroxide, sulphur and unattacked lead chromate. Particular care was taken in testing for sulphurous and thionic acids, which were, however, absent.

When analysed by the method shown on page 509; it was found that, at laboratory temperature (15-20°), only about 5% of the lead chromate were decomposed while, at 80-85°, 15-20% were attacked. Grinding the chromate in a mechanically operated agate mortar, increased the decomposition to about 30% and a slight further increase was obtained by passing hydrogen sulphide through a suspension of freshly precipitated lead chromate in 3 litres of water.

This showed that, if lead chromate could be obtained in a sufficiently fine state of division, complete interaction might be effected.

A suspension of 1 g. of lead chromate was obtained in 2 litres of water by mixing 1 litre each of potassium chromate and lead chloride in stoichiometric proportions. The hydrolysis of the lead chromate so produced was shown not to be excessive by a determination of the p_{H} value of the solution by the Comparator-indicator method. It was then mixed with about 4 litres of water saturated with hydrogen sulphide and allowed to stand overnight. Filtration was tedious and this is an important factor affecting the ultimate result. By this method, 90-95% of lead chromate were attacked.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Co-ordinated and Ionic Sulphate.

(i) The precipitate was transferred to two separate filter papers (a) and (b). One part (a) was extracted with 0.3N-KOH, which removes thiosulphate, sulphate and a portion of the lead chromate.

An aliquot portion of this extract was treated with barium chloride solution to precipitate sulphate and chromate. This precipitate was filtered on a weighed filter paper and washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, which dissolved out barium chromate, leaving barium sulphate unaffected. The weight of BaSO_4 indicates the total sulphate present. The chromic acid liberated was a measure of the unused lead chromate in that portion. The rest of the original precipitate (a) was extracted with HCl-NaCl solution (100 c.c. of a saturated solution of sodium chloride, 15 c.c. of water and 10 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid, $d_{1.19}$), the unattacked lead chromate dissolved liberating an equivalent amount of chromic acid, which was a measure of the unattacked lead chromate present.

(ii) The second portion of the precipitate (b), was directly extracted with HCl-NaCl solution and lead and sulphate estimated in it. A little sulphate would be formed by the oxidation of thio-sulphate to sulphate by chromic acid solution but, as the decomposition was 95% or more, the amount of sulphate so formed was relatively small.

The results in Table I show that the amounts of sulphate in the second determination (b), are much less than those found in the first (a), indicating that the sulphate is present in both the ionic and co-ordinate forms.

TABLE I.

Determination of the state of combination of the sulphate group in the final precipitate.

Hydrogen sulphide is passed into PbCrO_4 suspended in water at laboratory temperature and about 10% of the chromate is attacked.

	<i>a</i> Total (SO_4) for 1 g. Pb (KOH-extract).	<i>b</i> Ionic (SO_4) for 1g. Pb (HCl-NaCl-extract).	<i>a/b</i> .
1.	0.2043 g.	0.0767 g.	2.66
2.	0.3499	0.1476	2.37

Precipitates were ultimately analysed as follows:—

(a) The precipitate was extracted with 0·3N-KOH (approx.) and as a pale yellow liquid obtained in which sulphate, thiosulphate and unreacted chromate were estimated (Dunnicliff and Kotwani, *loc. cit.*).

(b) The residue after this extraction was treated with 5% sulphuric acid containing a little alcohol to extract chromium hydroxide as sulphate. The hydroxide was reprecipitated with ammonia and weighed as Cr₂O₃. Chromate was estimated after filtering off the chromium hydroxide.

(c) The residue from (b) was extracted with cold HCl-NaCl solution and any lead chromate still left, was determined as chromic acid. Direct extraction with NaCl-HCl solution which removes Pb as well as Cr₂O₃ is not feasible as it is not possible to estimate the Cr₂O₃ quickly in presence of the lead.

Table II gives the results of chromic oxide estimation in which residues of unattacked chromates are represented by the sum of the amount of chromate found in the three extracts, *a*, *b*, *c* (*vide supra*).

TABLE II.

Estimation of chromic oxide.

Started with lead chromate (1 g.).

Expt.	Wt. of unattacked lead chromate.	Lead chromate attacked.	Chromic acid present as hydroxide, sulphate and thiosulphate.	
			Expt.	Theory.
1. (a)	0·0544 g.			
	(b) 0·0163	92·47%	0·2154 g.	0·2176 g.
	(c) 0·0046			
0·0753				
2. (a)	0·0375			
	(b) 0·0163	94·62	0·2220	0·2225
	(c) 0·0000			
0·0538				
3 (a)	0·0326			
	(b) 0·0109	94·51	0·2220	0·2224
	(c) 0·0114			
0·0549				

Free sulphur was determined by oxidising all the sulphur products to sulphate with sodium peroxide and estimating the sulphate in excess of that obtainable from thiosulphate, sulphate and lead sulphide, as determined directly.

The results given in Table II are calculated as follows, mean values being used to illustrate the method. Assuming the reactions,

Also, on the assumption that hydrogen sulphide is oxidised to sulphate by the chromic acid produced.

The following reactions involving the formation of thiosulphate are assumed:—

The values for sulphate and thiosulphate, calculated for 100 g. of chromic acid from lead chromate, are about 3% higher than those obtained in the case of the reduction of chromic acid by hydrogen sulphide (Dunnicliff and Kotwani, *loc. cit.*) suggesting that the chromic acid obtained from PbCrO_4 is a more active oxidising agent and perhaps this is explainable from its method of formation.

In view of the fact that six to seven litres of water had to be used for these experiments, the extremely high values for sulphur are possibly due to the oxidation of hydrogen sulphide by the oxygen dissolved in water and taken up from the atmosphere and, to a minor degree, to photochemical action.

Oxygen dissolved in water was estimated by Winkler's method (*Ber.*, 1888, 21, 2843; *cf.* also *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1914, 53, 665; *C.F.C.A.*,

1915, 8, 674) and it was shown that this oxygen alone is sufficient to account for the excess of sulphur formed in the reaction.

TABLE III.

Values calculated for 100 g. of lead chromate actually attacked.

Expt.	1 g.	2 g.	3 g.	4 g.	5 g.
1. Thiosulphate (S ₂ O ₃)	2.3530	2.3729	2.3439	2.3080	2.3440
In terms of 100 g. of lead chromate (Eqn. 3, v.s.)					18.04%
2. Sulphate (SO ₄)	8.6260	8.5550	8.5610	8.4740	8.5540
In terms of 100 g. of lead chromate (Eqn. 2, v.s.)					76.81%
3. Sulphur (S) in the free state.	2.50	2.11	2.65	4.40	0.76
In terms of 100 g. of PbCrO ₄ (Eqn. 1, v.s.)					(Theory). 5.15 (by difference).
4. Chromic oxide (Cr ₂ O ₃)	23.54	23.50	23.46	...	23.50
In terms of 100 g. of PbCrO ₄					99.90%

Final greenish-black precipitate at 10°.

In various experiments performed under identical conditions, sulphate was estimated in the final precipitate both in the alkali and the HCl-NaCl extracts to see whether it was co-ordinated (Table IV). Lead chromate was treated in its finest state of division and about 95% were actually attacked.

TABLE IV.

Expt.	BaSO ₄ by HCl acid treatment. (a)	BaSO ₄ by KOH treatment. (b)	Ratio b : a.
1.	0.0279 g.	0.1767 g.	6.30 : 1.00
2.	0.0289	0.1767	6.28 : 1.00
3.	0.0290	0.1767	9.90 : 1.00

A comparison of the results with those shown in Table I indicates that, as the percentage of lead chromate decomposed increases, the precipitate undergoes further changes, resulting in the co-ordination of more sulphate at the expense of ionic sulphate. It is possible that,

when the lead chromate is quantitatively attacked, the whole of the sulphate might be co-ordinated.

Ignoring the values for sulphur, the analyses in Table III (slow reaction: H_2S on suspension at ordinary temperature) work out to the following equation:—

The effect of temperature.—When the reactants were mixed at 50° and 70° , the reaction was found to proceed much more rapidly. Estimations of sulphate and thiosulphate in the precipitate were carried out after extraction with potassium hydroxide. A comparison of the results with those shown in Table II, indicates that

(i) The slower the reaction, the greater the tendency to form thio-sulphate.

(ii) Possibly some sulphate is formed by the oxidation of thio-sulphate.

(iii) The greater activity of chromic acid produced from lead chromate is again emphasised.

TABLE V.

Final greenish-black precipitate.

Values are calculated per 100 g. of lead chromate actually attacked.

Expt	Temperature = 50° .					In terms of 100 g. PbCrO_4 .
	1 g.	2 g.	3 g.	4 g.		
1 Thiosulphate (S_2O_3)	2.20	2.24	2.31	2.25		17.31%
2 Sulphate (SO_4)	9.26	9.30	9.24	9.26		83.16
						<hr/> 100.47
Temperature = 70° .						
1 Thiosulphate (S_2O_3)	2.31	2.32	2.30	2.31		17.71
2 Sulphate (SO_4)	9.28	9.22	9.23	9.24		83.03
						<hr/> 100.74

Sulphate and thiosulphate represent 100.74% of the lead chromate thus accounting for the whole oxidising power of PbCrO_4 and sulphur should be entirely absent. Careful investigation, however, showed the presence of considerable amounts of sulphur. This may be attributed

to the oxidation of hydrogen sulphide by oxygen dissolved in water (*vide p.* 510) and that taken up from the surrounding air during the processes of filtration.

The free sulphur in the 'slow' reaction appears quantitatively as sulphate in the reaction accelerated by the higher temperature.

The Action of Hydrogen Sulphide on Silver Chromate.

Silver chromate was prepared in two varieties (i) red, by precipitation of a soluble silver salt with a chromate, and (ii) green, by dissolving the red variety in aqueous ammonia and reprecipitating by boiling the solution.

On treating a suspension of 1 g. of pure (red or green) silver chromate in water with about 500 c.c. of H₂S-water, a greenish black substance was ultimately obtained.

The filtrate and washings contained no compound of interest; the precipitate consisted of silver sulphide, chromium sulphate, thio-sulphate, sulphite and hydroxide, free sulphur and unattacked silver chromate.

The reaction was conducted in an apparatus in which the particles of silver chromate were ground between the stopper and neck of an inverted wide mouthed bottle from which the bottom had been cut, the stopper being fixed to the base inside a glass dish. The reaction was allowed to proceed in the bottle (which now presented the shape of a beaker with a grinding collar at the base) and, from time to time, it was carefully eased in its seating and rotated with gentle pressure to allow a small quantity of the suspension of partially attacked particles to pass out between the stopper and rotating neck which formed the grinding interface. The fresh surface thus presented was allowed to come in contact with more hydrogen sulphide in the outer vessel. After about two hours' grinding, the filtered residue contained no silver chromate, showing that the reaction was complete.

The products obtained as described for lead chromate were the same as those found in the "bottle" method which was used in all silver chromate work.

Sulphite, thiosulphate and sulphate occur co-ordinated either wholly or in part in a mixture of complex chromium compounds. Evidence on this point was obtained by extraction of the final precipitate with 5% hydrochloric acid. The remaining precipitate contained sulphite, thiosulphate and sulphate. On extraction with 10% HCl, however, the results were negative.

The appearance of sulphite in the final precipitate is of great importance.

Method of analysis.—The precipitate was extracted with 0.3N KOH and the filtrate and washings made up to a known volume. A few c.c. of glycerol were added to the extract to stabilise the sulphite against atmospheric oxidation (S. L. Bigelow, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, 26, 493). A colourless liquid was obtained in which sulphate, thiosulphate and sulphite were estimated, protecting the sulphite from iodine by the addition of formalin.

The results of these estimations are given in Table VI, values being calculated in a similar manner to those for lead using

48 g. S	}	331.76 g. Ag ₂ CrO ₄
36 g. (SO ₄)		
42 g. (S ₂ O ₃)		
and 40 g. (SO ₃)		

TABLE VI.

Final greenish-black precipitate.

Values are shown for 100 g. of Ag₂CrO₄ attacked.

Expt.	1 g.	2 g.	3 g.	4 g.	5 g.
1. Sulphite (SO ₃)	1.909	1.853	1.803	1.886	1.863
	In terms of 100 g. of silver chromate ...				15.44%
2. Thiosulphate (S ₂ O ₃)	4.724	4.724	4.724	4.724	4.724
	In terms of 100 g. of silver chromate ...				37.32%
3. Sulphate (SO ₄)	3.98	3.87	3.87	3.90	3.905
	In terms of 100 g. silver chromate ...				35.98%
4. Sulphur (S)	3.13	3.75	2.90		1.65 (theory)
	In terms of 100 g. of silver chromate ...				11.26 (by difference)
5. Chromic oxide (Cr ₂ O ₃)	22.86	22.86	22.89	22.84	22.86
	In terms of 100 g. of silver chromate ...				99.78%

The high values of sulphur are again attributable to the oxidation of hydrogen sulphide by, atmospheric oxygen and that dissolved in water.

The table below gives the amounts of lead and silver chromates, accounted for by the different sulphur-acid products.

TABLE VII.

Values are shown for 100 g.

	Sulphate.	Thiosulphate.	Sulphite.
In terms of PbCrO ₄	76·81	18·01	—
In terms of Ag ₂ CrO ₄	35·69	37·32	15·44

In the case of silver chromate, the values for sulphate diminish while thiosulphate increases and sulphite makes its appearance. From this it appears that sulphite and not thiosulphate, is the precursor of sulphate. Hence the authors favour the direct oxidation of sulphylic acid as the method of formation of sulphate.

This investigation will be completed in the publication of a further report at an early date when the conclusions from the series of five papers will be summarised.